

Kinetic Studies of the Reaction Between Bromine and Malic Acid (Influence of Hydrogen Ion Concentration)

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The kinetics of the oxidation of malic acid with bromine has been studied. The reaction was found to be of first order with respect to both bromine malic acid—the total order being two. The energy of activation, free energy and entropy of activation were found to be 14.0 K. cal./mole., 15.1 K. cal./mole. and -3.6 e. u. at $pH \sim 8.75$. The reaction rate increases, at first, with rise of pH , reaches a maximum at $pH \sim 9.40$ and, then, decreases. The dependence of the rate on pH showed that HOBr is a faster oxidising agent than molecular bromine. The reactive species was found to be a combination of hypobromous acid and bromine molecule with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$. The oxidation reaction can be represented by the attack of the oxidant on carboxylate ion.

A survey of literature revealed that malic acid has been estimated by different oxidising agents¹⁻³, but no attempt seems to have been made to oxidise malic acid stoichiometrically to carbon dioxide and water by bromine and to study its reaction mechanism.

Experimental

Materials :

All the chemicals used were B. D. H. 'AnalaR' products and were used without any further purification.

Stoichiometry of the reaction :

The data given in Table 1 show that the reaction between malic acid and bromine is quantitative and that the oxidation takes place to the stage of carbon dioxide and water. The production of carbon dioxide in the end products was tested quantitatively.

Procedure for Kinetic studies :

The procedure given in an earlier communication³ was followed in this case.

Results and Discussions :

The reaction has been shown to be of first order with respect to each of the reactants (Table 2)—the total order being two. The results in (Table 1) indicate the stoichiometry of the reaction and those in Table 3 show that the reaction is fastest at $pH \sim 9.40$. The rate constant decreases with the increase of bromide ion concentration (Table 5) which shows that the reaction with hypobromous acid is faster than that with molecular bromine. The energy of activation, free energy and entropy of activation were 14.0 K. cal./mole, 15.1 K. cal./mole. and -3.6 e.u. at $pH \sim 8.75$ (Table 4).

Experimentally, it has been shown that no complex formation is involved in the system as shown by the plot of $1/k$, against $1/\text{sodium malate}$

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	Time=6 hours		Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$		pH~9		
	Malic acid taken (ml.)	"Br ₂ " (0.025 M) added (ml.)	"Br ₂ " (0.025 M) consumed (ml.)	Malic acid present (gm.)	Malic acid found (gm.)	% Recovery	% Error \pm
1.	5.00	5.00	3.60	0.00279	0.00202	Incomplete	—
2.	5.00	10.00	5.01	0.00279	0.00381	100.72	+0.72
3.	6.00	15.00	6.00	0.00335	0.00336	100.30	+0.30
4.	5.00	15.00	5.02	0.00279	0.00281	100.72	+0.72
5.	8.00	25.00	8.02	0.00447	0.00449	100.45	+0.45
6.	8.00	30.00	8.01	0.00447	2.00449	100.45	+0.45
7.	5.00	20.00	5.02	0.00279	0.00281	100.72	+0.72
8.	6.00	25.00	6.02	0.00335	0.00337	100.60	+0.60

TABLE 2

FIRST ORDER CONSTANT WITH RESPECT TO HYPOBROMITE

 Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

 Hypobromite = $0.95 \times 10^{-3} M$ Sodium thiosulphate = $0.001 N$

 Sodium Malate $\times 10^{-3}$ 20.00 16.66 12.50 11.11

 $k_1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$ 47.20 39.10 29.40 26.10

 $k_1/\text{sodium malate}$ 2.3600 2.3469 2.3526 2.3492

 Mean value of $k_1/\text{sodium malate} = 2.3522 \pm 0.0078 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$

FIRST ORDER CONSTANT WITH RESPECT TO MALIC ACID

 Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

 Hypobromite = $11.30 \times 10^{-3} M$ Sodium thiosulphate = $0.01 N$

 Sodium malate = $0.188 \times 10^{-3} M$ Mean pH = 8.10

 $k_1 = 0.42 \times 10^{-3} M \text{ min}^{-1}$

TABLE 3

SECOND ORDER CONSTANTS

 Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

 Hypobromite = $5.60 - 6.07 \times 10^{-3} M$

 Malic acid = $0.933 - 1.013_k \times 10^{-3} M$

Mean pH	k litre mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$
3.15	0.13
4.75	5.13
6.00	12.00
6.70	16.67
7.45	17.33
8.75	18.00
8.85	24.00 (0.025 M sulphate)
8.85	16.00 (0.025 M chloride)
9.40	20.00
9.80	19.33
10.65	6.00
12.10	2.66

TABLE 4

SECOND ORDER CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT

TEMPERATURES

 Bromine = $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ Malic acid = $0.917 - 1.008 \times 10^{-3} M$

 Hypobromite = $5.50 - 6.05 \times 10^{-3} M$ Mean pH = 8.78

Temp. °C	k litre mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$
35	18.00
40	26.00
45	30.00

TABLE 5

EFFECT OF ADDED BROMIDE

 Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$

 Bromine = $6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ Malic acid = $1.033 \times 10^{-3} M$

 Hypobromite = $6.20 \times 10^{-3} M$ Mean pH = 6.50

Br ⁻ Concentration	k litre mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$
Nil	12.00
0.20 M	8.66
0.25 M	6.00
0.33 M	4.00

when a straight line passing through the origin was obtained (Table 2, Fig. 1). The absence of a free

radical is indicated by the negative test with mercuric chloride. The fact that the reaction is fast in the

Fig. 1. Sodium malate vs Bromine

alkaline medium (pH ~ 9.40) agrees quantitatively with the assumption that the anion of the substrate is oxidised much more rapidly than the undissociated molecule.

Reactive species :

On the basis of arguments advanced in the earlier communication, two possibilities⁴ could be considered viz., (i) $k_{\text{HOBr}} \gg k_{\text{Br}_2}$ and (ii) $k_{\text{HOBr}} \ll k_{\text{Br}_2}$. The value of K_1 ($K_1 = 32.3 \times 10^{-9}$) obtained on the basis of assumption I is nearer to the accepted value⁵ (indicated by a cross on the x axis (Fig. 2),

$$\left[1 + \frac{c}{K_3} - \frac{k_{\text{Br}_2}}{k_{\text{obsd}}} \right]$$

Fig. 2. Malic acid vs Bromine

but the value of K_1 ($K_1 = 119.70 \times 10^{-9}$) obtained on the basis of II assumption differs from the theoretical value. The statement that $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ is supported by these results. The reactive species, therefore, is a combination of hypobromous acid and molecular bromine with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$. This is supported by the results with bromine free hypobromous acid which was prepared by the method of Y. Knoller and B. Perlmutter-Hayman⁶. The value of k with unbuffered and buffered hypobromous acid was found to be 6.66 and 6.00 respectively.

Besides, a plot of rate constant based on Table 3, Fig. 3, against the calculated concentrations of $[HBrO] \times [C_4H_5O_7^-]$ at the middle stage of the

Fig 3. Malic acid vs Bromine

—●— Calculated values of concentrations at the middle stage $[HBrO] \times [H_2C_4O_7] \times 10^5$
 ...×... Experimental values of rate constant $\times 1.1 \times 10^4$

reaction showed a close parallelism. The slowing down of the reaction beyond $pH \sim 9.40$ is due to the decrease in the concentrations of $HOBr$ and Br_2 , Br_3 does not take part in the oxidation reaction.

TABLE 6

EXPERIMENTAL VALUE OF RATE CONSTANT AT 35°			CALCULATED VALUES OF CONCENTRATIONS AT MIDDLE STAGE OF 25°	
pH	k $\times 10^{-3}$	pH	$[HBrO + Br_2] \times [H_2C_4O_7] \times 10^5$	$[HBrO] \times [H_2C_4O_7^-] \times 10^5$
3.15	0.13	2	3.47	2.79×10^{-5}
4.75	5.13	3	29.70	23.83×10^{-4}
6.00	12.00	4	120.80	96.51×10^{-3}
6.70	16.67	5	174.12	13.89×10^{-1}
7.45	17.38	6	187.04	18.90
8.75	18.00	7	221.89	98.95
9.40	20.00	8	248.97	220.98
9.80	19.39	9	103.99	102.99
10.65	6.00	10	19.39	14.89
12.10	2.66	11	1.60	1.56
—	—	12	0.160	0.15
—	—	13	0.016	0.015

Rate constants :

Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific rate constant K_1 (Table 2) and K_2 (Table 3) obtained from the slope of $\log(a-x)$ and $1/(a-x)$ respectively against time in seconds. The hypobromite content of the solution was determined by arsenite method⁷ and used for calculation of the rate constants.

Reaction mechanism :

Here, the assumption that, both, hypobromous acid and molecular-bromine act as oxidising agents with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ holds good. Hypobromous acid oxidises malic acid to tartaric acid which is oxidised to carbon dioxide and water through the intermediary of glyoxylic acid as shown below :—

Separate experiments on the oxidation of tartarate ion by bromine showed that the reaction is comparatively slower while the oxidation of glyoxylic acid by bromine is a fast reaction.

Similarly, equations can be written with Br_2 as the other reactive species. However, it has been shown that glyoxylic acid is oxidised much more rapidly by hypobromous acid than by molecular bromine.

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